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Trend Analysis of Share Prices on the Bombay Stock Exchange

Dharen Kumar Pandey*

Mukesh Kumar**

Abstract

The oil and gas sector is one of the booming sectors in the Indian economy. This study aims at testing whether all the companies of a particular sector follow the same pattern in a given period of time. Behavioural studies have been a topic of controversy for long time. In general, two types of analysis are used to ascertain the price behaviour of the shares; viz; technical analysis and fundamental analysis. In this study, we have concentrated over the technical analysis. Our results explicated that a certain group of companies from a particular industry follows a similar pattern when it calls for the price changing behaviour of its shares in the stock market.

Keywords : Technical analysis, Fundamental analysis, Behavioural aspects, Trend analysis, Return.

Introduction

Share price behaviour refers to the trend followed by the share prices in the stock market including the open, high, low and close prices. The movement of the share prices over a period of time is referred to as the price behaviour. The study of the share price behaviour has always been in controversy regarding the indices under analysis. Some argue that share price index do not represent the real characteristics of the share. However, researchers have been studying the price behaviour with help of the fundamental and the technical analysis. The fundamental analysis holds that the share price depends upon the fundamental factors of the industry as well as the company, whereas, the technical analysis concludes with help of the share prices over a period of time placed on a chart (hence, also known as chartist method). Above all, the efficient market hypothesis holds that in an efficient market neither the fundamental nor the technical analysis is valuable. In an efficient market, it is assumed that the investors are provided with all the information relevant to the stock market and hence, the previous price changes and the fundamental factors will have no effect over the share prices in the future. According to Fama, there exist three forms of efficiency in the stock market: weak form, semi-strong form, and strong form of market efficiency. Indian stock market is considered to have weak form efficiency where the market has a very fast effect rather than that of a long term effect for any information, say a bonus issue or a dividend announcement.

Oil and gas industry is one of the booming sectors in the economy and the share prices of this sector will definitely follow a similar pattern as followed by the other booming sectors. Oil and Natural Gas Corporation (ONGC) and Reliance Industries Ltd (RIL) are the leaders in this sector. A comparative study of these companies will definitely results in drawing some inferences relevant to the topic under preview.

Objective

The main aim of the paper is to test whether all the companies of a particular sector follow the same pattern in case of the price changing behaviour of the shares. For this purpose we have considered one of the leading sectors, viz; the Oil and Gas Sector. The trend followed by the average returns from the shares of these companies during the aforesaid was also analysed. It also aims at conceptualising the recession effect over the share prices of the shares of these companies.

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Scope and Research Methodology

The study covers the price change pattern of only the oil and gas companies in India. Also for the study, only two companies from this sector have been selected; viz. ONGC and RIL. These two companies were compared because these two companies were among the top 30 blue-chip companies listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange and hence considered to be the leaders. With an assumption that the sector follows their leaders, the analysis for these companies was moved forward upon. With a post-liberalisation view, the data for 15 year period 1996-2011 was collected from the BSE website. Data for RIL was available from 1991 but for ONGC it was available only from 1996. So in order to neutralize the effects, the data for RIL was considered from 1996. The data results were used for T-test using the SPSS technique. The open-high-low-close chart was also used to present the price change behaviour of the shares of these two companies. In order to analyse the recession effect, the OHLC chart for the month of April 2008 has also been prepared for both these companies.

Quantitative Analysis

For the purpose of analysis, daily open and close prices of ONGC and RIL have been collected from the BSE website for the period 1996-2011. With the help of the open and close prices, the daily return was calculated. These daily returns resulted in the average return for every year for each company. It should also be noted that the previous day closing was considered as the opening price for the following day. These data have been tabulated and used for calculating the returns. In this way we got daily return for the 15 year period. Average annual return has been calculated for every year. Table 1 shows the average annual return for both the companies for 15 years. These average annual returns of both the companies were used to test the following hypotheses:

H_0 : There was no difference between the share price changes of ONGC and RIL

H_1 : There was difference between the share price changes of ONGC and RIL

Table-1: Average Annual Returns for the period 1996-2011

Year	ONGC	RIL
1996-97	0.041223	0.14937844
1997-98	0.161809	-0.0370194
1998-99	-0.31007	-0.0465283
1999-00	0.125705	0.39180171
2000-01	0.025838	0.11352842
2001-02	0.334822	-0.0665684
2002-03	0.137392	-0.015634
2003-04	0.377109	0.28109315
2004-05	0.043655	0.02824367
2005-06	0.170183	0.17756196
2006-07	-0.11121	0.24153594
2007-08	0.081616	0.2336365
2008-09	-0.04903	-0.0884012
2009-10	0.167643	-0.0257531
2010-11	-0.24468	0.00198346

*Data calculated with the help of share prices as available on BSE website

The Hypothesis was tested with help of T-test at 95% confidence level with a sample size of 15 (less than 30). Comparing means will help in drawing the inference whether the share prices of both the companies have experienced the same pattern or not. It can easily be concluded with help of the T-test whether the null hypothesis is accepted or rejected.

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Table-2: Group Statistics

	Companies	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Average	ONGC	15	.0634675	.18775663	.04847855
	RIL	15	.0892573	.14884467	.03843153

Table 2 explicates the group statistics used for the T-test. The first sample consisted of the Annual Average Return of the ONGC where the total No. of observation was 15 (n=15) with a mean of 0.0634675 and a standard deviation of 0.18775663. The Standard Error mean was 0.04847855. The second sample consisted of the Annual Average Return of the RIL with the same sample size with a mean of 0.0892573, a standard deviation of 0.14884467 and the Standard error mean of 0.03843153. It can easily be seen that the mean of the annual average return was higher in the case of RIL, but however the results of the T-test revealed that both the companies experienced the same pattern in share price changes.

Table-3: Independent T-test Results

	T-test for Equality of Means						
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% confidence Interval of the Difference	
						Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	-0.417	28	0.680	-0.02578976	0.06186398	-0.15251238	0.10093287

*T-test with the help of SPSS

The T-test revealed that the calculated value of T (-0.417) was in negative and less than the critical value at 95% confidence interval and 28 degrees of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It was concluded that the shares of both the companies followed the same behavioural pattern in the stock exchange.

Figure-1: Annual Average Return for ONGC and RIL for the period 1996-2011

Figure 1 illustrates that although the annual average return for RIL was comparatively more than that of ONGC but both follows the same pattern. When the AAR for RIL follows upward trend, the AAR of ONGC also follows the same and vice-versa. It also explicates that both companies follow an upward and downward trend simultaneously. One year it goes up and the other year it comes down for the complete 15 year period.

Figure-2: Consolidated Open-High-Low-Close Chart of RIL

The open-high-low-close chart usually explicates the short term price behaviour of any share. The short term OHLC chart has been merged in to a single chart for the period 1996-2001. Figure 2 explicates the price behaviour for the shares of the RIL. For the first ten years the performance of the shares were average but the next five years (2006-2011) there were frequent changes in the share prices. It can easily be seen how speedily the price crossed Rs.3200 in 2008 and a tremendous fall brought it down to RS. 1000 in the same year. This tremendous fall was the resultant of the global financial crisis which started from the US and the UK economies. Although after this slow down it recovered itself and went up to Rs. 2500 in the following year but again returned back to Rs. 1000. For the last one and half years, it remained constant at the level between Rs. 900-Rs. 1100.

Figure-3: Consolidated Open-High-Low-Close Chart of ONGC

Figure 3 explicates the price behavior for the shares of the ONGC. For the first eight years(1996-2003) the performance of the shares were average. The share prices lies between Rs.100 to Rs.400 but the next seven years (2004-2011) there were frequent changes in the share prices. The share prices were increased after 2002 till 2006. In the term of 1996-2011 the highest share prices of ONGC was Rs. 1550 in the year 2006 but after the year 2006, the share prices came down from Rs.1550 to Rs.800. Although it recovered itself and went up to Rs. 1400 in the following year but again returned back to Rs. 600. One reason for this being the economic slowdown. Again in the mid year between 2010 to 2011 the share prices increased and it went up to Rs.1500.

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Figure-4: OHLC Chart for ONGC for the month of April 2008-09

Figure 4 represents the OHLC chart for the ONGC shares for the month of April 2008. It clearly depicts that out of 20 trading days, 13 trading days experienced a down bar (closing price lower than the opening price), i.e. the investors got a negative return (loss), while only 7 trading days experienced an up bar (closing price higher than opening price), i.e. the investors got a positive return (profit) and that, too, with a very less difference. Thus it can be said that there was an effect of the ongoing recession during the period over the share prices.

Figure-5: OHLC Chart for RIL for the month April of 2008-09

Figure 5 represents the OHLC chart for the RIL shares for the month of April 2008. It can be seen that out of 20 trading days 10 trading days experienced a down bar (closing price lower than the opening price) while the other 10 trading days experienced an upward bar (closing price higher than opening price). Upward bars have been in an increasing order which is said to be good but in the second last week we can see that the down bars are continuously falling down, thus, a warning bell for the investors. The recession had some effect over the RIL share prices during that period.

However, the OHLC charts depicts that both the companies followed nearly a similar pattern in the price changing behaviour in the stock market. In the beginning of the period under study, both followed an average trend with a rise in between followed by a downfall due to the global economic crisis which went on the Indian economy for some period.

Conclusion and Suggestions

The above analysis concludes that all the oil and gas companies are following similar pattern in the share price changes. Although the analysis has been done for two companies only but these companies are the leaders in this sector. It has always been assumed that the market follow the leaders. So, it can be concluded on basis of the results based on the study of these two

companies, that all the oil and gas companies have followed an average trend with an expected minimum return of during the period. The OHLC chart, too, represents that share price changes in both the companies followed a similar pattern. It is also found during the analysis that the ongoing recession during the period has led to a short term effect over the shares of the oil and gas companies. It can also be concluded that whatever be the market conditions, the shares of a group of companies from a particular industry follow each other when it comes for price variations. One of the reasons behind this may be the continuous eye of the investors over the particular industry which may guide them in a neutralised portfolio. They know when to invest, what amount to invest and where to invest. This may be, for instance, that when a particular sector is booming, investors may invest in the shares of about all the companies belonging to this sector. This is how all the companies in a particular sector will follow a similar pattern irrelevant of other factors. It is suggested to the investors that they can consider the predictions, of the leading companies in a group of companies, for investment in any particular company which belongs to that group. Keeping an eye upon the leaders will help forecast the price variations of that group.

References :

1. Aktham, M. and Ahmad, A. (2007). Oil prices and stock markets in GCC countries: new evidence from non-linear cointegration. *Journal of Managerial Finance*, 33 (7), 449-460.
2. Al-Mudaf, Anwar, A, Goodwin, Thomas H. (1993). Oil shocks and Oil stocks: an evidence from 1970s. *Applied Economics*, 25, 181-190.
3. Boyer, Martin M. and Fillion, Didier. (2009). Common and fundamental factors in stock returns of Canadian oil and gas companies. *Energy Economics*, 29, 428-453.
4. Chakrovorty, S (2006). Stock Market and macroeconomic behaviour in India. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.112.5953&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.
5. Cologni, A, Manera, M. (2008). Oil prices, inflation and interest rates in a structural cointegrated VAR model for the G-7 countries. *Energy Economics*, 30, 856-888.
6. Hayo, B, Kutan, A. (2005). The impact of news, oil prices, and global market developments on Russian financial markets. *Economics of Transition*, Volume 13 (2), 373-393.
7. M. Thenmozhi (2001). Market Value Added and Share Price Behaviour: An Empirical Study of BSE Sensex Companies. *Delhi Business Review*. Vol 1, No 1. Retrieved from http://www.delhibusiness-review.org/v_1n1/dbrv1n1g.pdf.
8. Michael Firth, (1975) "The Efficient Market Theory of Share Price Behaviour", *Managerial Finance*, Vol. 1 Issue 3, pp.184 – 188. Retrieved from <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/journals.htm?articleid=1648687&show=abstract>.
9. Pani, U. (2007). Dividend Policy and Stock Price Behaviour in Indian Corporate Sector: A panel data approach. Retrieved from http://www.igidr.ac.in/conf/money/mfc-12/Coporate_Dividendpolicy_and_stock_price_behaviour_upananda%20pani.pdf.
10. Pradhan, R.S. and Upadhyay, B.D. (2006). The Efficient Market Hypothesis and the Behaviour of Share Prices in Nepal. *Research in Nepalese Finance*. Kathmandu: Buddha Academics.
11. Skaradzinski, D.A. (2003). The Nonlinear Behavior of Stock Prices: The Impact of Firm Size, Seasonality, and Trading Frequency. Dissertation submitted to the Faculty of the Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University. Retrieved from <http://scholar.lib.vt.edu/theses/available/etd-11242003-223654/unrestricted/SkaradzinskiNonlinearBehaviorofStockPrices.pdf>.
12. Thompson, S. (1999). Modelling Share Price Behaviour across Time. Retrieved from http://www.bus.qut.edu.au/faculty/schools/economics/documents/discussionPapers/1999/Thompson_Lead_71.pdf.